

Original Article

Prevalence of Cardiovascular Disease Risk Factors among Adults in a Slum of Dhaka City

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Abstract

Background: Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is one of the leading causes of death worldwide. Slum living communities are increasingly adopting urban lifestyles and becoming more vulnerable to the risk of developing CVD.

Objective: This study aimed to estimate the prevalence of risk factors of cardiovascular disease among adults living in a slum in Dhaka city.

Methods: It was a cross-sectional survey conducted on conveniently selected 461 people in the Agargaon slum area. A face-to-face interview was taken by using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by using WHO STEP wise Surveillance (STEPS) questionnaire with minor adaptation. Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 17). The χ^2 tests and Student's t-test were used as appropriate. The obtained information was presented in the form of tables and graphs. P value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

Results: Overall prevalence of smoking tobacco and smokeless tobacco use was 181(39.3%) and 219(47.5%) respectively. Based on MET minutes/week, 167(36.2%) of the study participants fell into the low physical activity category. None of them consumed adequate fruit or vegetables on an average day. Only 11(9%) percent of males consumed more than the recommended level of oil daily, whereas it was 77(35.2%) in the case of females. Mean salt consumption per day was 13.2 (SD \pm 3.79) grams, which was more than double the recommended level. The prevalence of overweight and obesity was 15.6%. The prevalence of high waist circumference was significantly higher in females than in males (45.5% versus 12.4%). The overall prevalence of hypertension was 14.8%.

Conclusion: This study showed a high prevalence of cardiovascular disease risk factors like both smoking and smokeless tobacco use, low physical activity, very minimum fruit, and vegetable intake with very high salt intake. Prevalence of hypertension was also found high. The study may help the policymakers in designing policies and programs for the prevention of CVDs in Bangladesh, which will be beneficial not only for slum people but also for the whole population of the country.

Keywords: Cardiovascular disease, Risk factor, Prevalence, Slum population.

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Introduction

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is a major health problem throughout the world and a common cause of premature morbidity and mortality. According to World Health Organization (WHO), CVDs are the number one cause of death globally. An estimated 17.9 million people died from CVDs in 2019, representing 32% of all global deaths.¹ Out of the 17 million premature deaths (under the age of 70) due to noncommunicable diseases in 2019, 38% were caused by CVDs.¹ Over three-quarters of CVD deaths take place in low- and middle-income countries.¹ Of these deaths, 85% were due to heart attack and stroke.¹ The number of people who die from CVDs, mainly from heart disease and stroke, will increase to reach 23.3 million by 2030.^{2,3} CVDs are projected to remain the single leading cause of death.² Over 80% of CVD deaths take place in low- and middle-income countries.³ South Asians represent one of the largest and fastest-growing ethnic groups in the world and they are experiencing epidemics of cardiovascular disease. CVD accounts for 27% of deaths in Bangladesh due to all causes.⁴

The major cardiovascular disease risk factors include tobacco use, unhealthy diet (low fruit and vegetable; high salt and oil consumption), physical inactivity, harmful alcohol consumption, overweight, and obesity, raised blood pressure, raised blood glucose, and abnormal blood lipids.⁵ CVDs and their associated known risk factors account for 13.4% of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) lost in Bangladesh.⁶ Among the five South Asian countries, Bangladeshis have the highest prevalence of CVD risk factors-hypertension (14.3%), obesity (43.3%), current and previous smoking (59.9%), low physical activity (98.7%), and low daily consumption of fruits and

vegetables (91.4%).⁷ Bangladesh also has the highest prevalence of diabetes mellitus (8% of adults age 18+)⁸ in Asia after China and India and the increase could increase by 13% by 2030⁹. Exposer of at least one risk factor of CVD is also very high in Bangladesh, 99.6% among men and 97.9% among women.^{7,10}

In recent years, several studies in Bangladesh have shown a high prevalence of cardiovascular disease and its negative impact on survival but few studies have focused on slum populations. Bangladesh is one of the most densely populated countries in the world and Dhaka city's population is about 17.6 million, of which an estimated 3.4 million people live in some 5000 slums.¹¹ These slum populations, though they represent a large part of the urban population are always neglected. They do not get proper health care and education and they are not even aware of their risk of developing diseases. In this population-based study on persons living in a slum of Dhaka city, we seek to determine the prevalence of risk factors related to cardiovascular disease among the slum population, which if properly addressed will help policymakers and health care providers to take appropriate decisions regarding this matter.

Materials And Methods**Study Design**

This was a cross-sectional study done in the Agargaon slum area of Dhaka city from July 2014 to June 2015. WHO STEPS chronic disease risk factor surveillance guideline was followed in this study. As resource was limited, only the first two steps i.e., questionnaire and physical measurements were done for this study. A total of 461 slum men and women aged 35 years and above were interviewed face to face in their households.

Data collection

Data was collected by using a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed with a minor adaptation of the WHO STEP wise Surveillance (STEPS) questionnaire. All the core variables along with some expanded variables from step 1 were incorporated. From step 2 physical measurements (height, weight, waist circumference, and blood pressure) were included. Informed consent was taken prior interview. Along with socio-demographic information, behavioral habit, information on hypertension and diabetes mellitus, anthropometric measurement (height, weight, waist circumference) as well as the measurement of blood pressure was done. Height, weight, and waist circumference were measured to calculate their body mass index (BMI), thereby obesity. The standing height was measured with a stadiometer without shoes. The body weight was measured with minimal clothing using a digital weighing scale Beurer GS 235. Waist circumference was measured by a plastic measuring tape, maintaining the privacy of the participants. Blood pressure was measured in a sitting position, with the calf at the level of the heart. After 5 minutes of rest, a second reading was taken. If the difference between the two readings was more than 5 mm of Hg, a third reading was taken.

Variables- Definition and Measurement

Tobacco use: The smoking status of the participants was categorized into 'current smoker' those who have smoked tobacco in the past 30 days and 'daily smoker' those who smoke any tobacco products every day.⁶

Smoking forms of tobacco include biri, cigarette (both manufactured and roll your own-RYO), pipe, cigars, and water pipe which is also known as shisha, hookah, or hubble-bubble.¹²

Smokeless tobacco includes jarda, sada pata, snuff like gul, betel nut, chewing tobacco e.g., plug, loose-leaf, chimo, toombak, guthha or twist, betel leaf, etc.¹²

Low fruit and vegetable consumption: Intake of fewer than 5 servings a day was considered low fruit and vegetable consumption. Servings were measured by showing the pictorial show cards or using measuring cups.⁶

High salt and oil consumption: To measure high salt and oil consumption, participants were asked about how much oil and salt they usually buy in a month and

converted that amount to per person per day by dividing the total quantity by the number of family members and thirty. Salt intake of more than 5 grams/day was considered high.¹³ Oil consumption of more than 25 ml (for men) and more than 20 ml (for women) was considered high.¹⁴

Physical activity: Measured according to the WHO Global Physical Activity Questionnaire method.¹⁵ Physical activities were measured by asking the respondents about their weekly and daily vigorous and moderate activities during work and leisure time, activities related to transport, and time spent in a sedentary position. All type of physical activities was transferred in minutes per day. Then the total duration was converted into metabolic equivalents (MET minutes/week). One MET was defined as the energy cost of sitting quietly for 1 minute and is equivalent to a caloric consumption of 1 kcal/kg/hour. MET-minute was calculated according to the STEPS protocol. All MET minutes for different forms of physical activities were added together to get total physical activities in MET minutes. Then physical activities were categorized into high, moderate, and low types. MET minutes 3000 or more per week were categorized as high physical activity group, 600 up to 3000 per week as moderate physical activity and less than 600 MET minutes per week as low activity.

Alcohol consumption: Alcohol consumption was measured by asking the respondents if they consumed ever, within the past 12 months, and within the past 30 days. Who drank within the past 30 days was defined as a *Current drinker*, who drink daily as a *Daily drinker*, who drank in the past 12 months as an *Alcohol consumer* and 5 or more drinks on a single occasion for men or 4 or more drinks on a single occasion for women, generally within about 2 hours as *Binge drinkers*.¹⁶

Obesity: Measured by calculating BMI. BMI was calculated as weight in kilograms divided by height in meters squared and then categorized into four groups: <18.5, 18.5–24.9, 25–29.9, and ≥ 30 kg/m².¹⁷

Waist circumference: Increased when it was ≥ 94 cm in men and ≥ 80 cm in women.¹²

Hypertension: Defined as SBP ≥ 140 mmHg, DBP ≥ 90 mmHg, or the use of any anti-hypertensive medication.¹⁸

Diabetes: A person was considered to have diabetes if she/he was previously diagnosed by a physician as diabetic and was under treatment or not.

Ethical considerations

All participants gave their written informed consent for inclusion before they participated in the study. The study was approved by the Ethical Review Committee of Bangladesh University of Health Sciences (Identification number: BUHS-ERC/EC/15/001) on 8th January 2015.

Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 17). Univariate, bivariate, and multivariate analysis was done. The obtained information was presented in the form of tables and graphs. Descriptive statistics such as mean, SD, frequency, and percentage were used as applicable. To test the differences between men and women for each categorical data variable, the χ^2 test was applied. The student's t-test was used for testing the mean differences of continuous variables between genders. The statistical tests were considered significant at a level of $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

A total of 461 adult slum people were interviewed in this study. A nearly equal proportion of men 241(52.3%) and women 220(47.7%) participated with a mean age of 43.0 ± 8.9 years. About two-thirds of participants 285(61.8%) were in the age range of 35 to 45 years. More than half of the participants (56.6%) had no formal education and only one-fourth (25.2%) completed more than the primary level of education. Females were mostly 180(81.8%) household workers, whereas about one-third (32.9%) of the males were engaged in different kinds of laborious work. About three-fourth 352 (76.4%) of the respondent's monthly family income was below 15000 BDT (180 US dollars).

Prevalence of Behavioral Risk Factors

The overall prevalence of smoking was 39.3%, it was 73.4% among men, and 1.8% among women. The prevalence of smoking was found significantly higher among males ($p < 0.05$). The overall prevalence of smokeless tobacco use was 47.5% and it was significantly higher among females than males ($p < 0.05$). Based on MET minutes/week, a little more than one-third (36.2%) of the participants fell into the low physical activity category (< 600 MET minutes/week), 32.8% fell into the moderate physical activity category

(600–3000 MET minutes/week) and 31% fell into high physical activity group (> 3000 MET minutes/week). Prevalence of high physical activity was more in males compared to females (43.6% vs 17.3%) and low physical activity was more in females compared to males (40.0% vs 32.8%). Alcohol consumption (drinking wine in the last 12 months) was found in only 3.5% of males. The survey population took fruit on an average of 2.4 ± 1.6 days a week. Vegetable consumption was quite high. They consumed vegetables around 5.8 ± 0.8 days a week. But neither fruit nor vegetable consumption was adequate in quantity. Considering 5 servings per day as the minimum recommended amount, none of the study participants did not consume adequate fruit or vegetable on an average day. Of the 241 males, only 122 persons could be assessed for their oil and salt consumption and of the 220 females, only one person could not tell about her oil and salt consumption. Only 9% of males consume more than the recommended level of oil daily, whereas it was 35.2% in the case of females ($p < 0.05$). A total of 338 (99.1%) participants consume salt more than their normal requirement. Almost all (97.2%) participants took extra salt while taking food (Table I).

Prevalence of Biological Risk Factors

The prevalence of overweight- obese was found at 15.6%. A little more than one-fourth of the respondents (28.2%) waist circumference was found high, for males and females, it was 12.4% and 45.5% respectively. The prevalence of high waist circumference was significantly higher in females than in males ($p < 0.05$). The overall prevalence of hypertension was 14.8% and it was 16.6% and 12.7% respectively among males and females. The prevalence of diabetes was found at 5.8% and 4.1% respectively among men and women (Table-II).

Frequency of risk factors among participants

Out of 461 respondents, a total of 341 slum people could be assessed for salt and oil consumption and all of them had the risk factor of high salt and oil consumption. Considering these 120 participants without any record of salt and oil consumption, no participants were found without a minimum of 2 risk factors. The prevalence of 5 risk factors was found highest (30.8%), followed by 4 risk factors (19.5%) (Table-III).

Table I: Prevalence of behavioral risk factors

Behavioral Risk Factors	Male (n=241)	Female (n=220)	Total n=461(100)	<i>p-value</i>
Tobacco use				
Smoking tobacco				
Current smoker	177(73.4)	4(1.8)	181(39.3)	0.000
Daily smoker	173(97.7)	2(50.0)	175(96.7)	0.000
Smokeless tobacco				
Current smokeless tobacco user	87(36.1)	132(60.0)	219(47.5)	0.000
Daily smokeless tobacco user (n=219, male-87, female-132)	69(79.3)	119(90.2)	188(85.8)	0.024
Physical activity				
Low physical activity	79(32.8)	88(40.0)	167(36.2)	0.000
Moderate physical activity	57(23.7)	94(42.7)	151(32.8)	
High physical activity	105(43.6)	38(17.3)	143(31.0)	
Alcohol consumption				
Current drinker	8(3.3)	0(0.0)	8(1.7)	0.00
Daily drinker	4(1.7)	0(0.0)	4(0.9)	
Binge drinker	4(1.7)	0(0.0)	4(0.9)	
Fruit and vegetable intake				
Mean days of fruits intake in a week	2.4±1.6	2.3±1.6	2.4 ± 1.6	0.931
Mean days of vegetable intake in a week	5.7±0.9	5.9±0.8	5.8 ± 0.8	0.010
Low fruit consumption	241(100)	220(100)	461(100)	
Low vegetable consumption	241(100)	220(100)	461(100)	
Oil consumption				
High oil consumption (n=341, male-122, female-219)	11(9.0)	77(35.1)	88(25.8)	0.000
Salt consumption				
High salt consumption	121(99.2)	217(99.1)	338(99.1)	0.929
Extra salt intake(n=461)	232(96.3)	216(98.2)	448(97.2)	0.214

Table II: Biological risk factors among the respondents

Risk factors	Male (n=241)	Female (n=220)	Total n=461(100)	p-value
Overweight and obesity				
Mean BMI in kg/m ²	22.2±2.80	22.55±3.04	22.37±2.92	0.202
Overweight and obese	32(13.3)	40(18.2)	72(15.6)	0.093
Waist circumference				
Mean waist circumferences in cm	81.36±8.04	78.16±6.97	79.83±7.71	0.000
High waist circumference	30(12.4)	100(45.5)	130(28.2)	0.000
Blood pressure				
Hypertension	40(16.6)	28(12.7)	68(14.8)	0.242
Previously diagnosed diabetes	14(5.8)	9(4.1)	23(5.0)	0.397

Table III: Frequency of risk factors among participants

Sex	2 risk factors	3 risk factors	4 risk factors	5 risk factors	6 or more risk factors	p-value
Male	22(4.8)	53(11.5)	51(11.1)	75(16.3)	40(8.6)	
Female	20(4.3)	45(9.8)	39(8.5)	67(14.5)	49(10.6)	
Overall Prevalence	42(9.1)	98(21.3)	90(19.5)	142(30.8)	89(19.2)	0.782

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this was the first CVD risk factor survey among the urban slum population in Bangladesh. The study participants, mostly rural migrants who had come to Dhaka for economic reasons and residing in the slums showed a very high prevalence of smoking tobacco use in males and smokeless tobacco use in females, a sedentary lifestyle, and low physical activity with very minimum exercise, very much inadequate fruit and vegetable consumption with high salt intake with invariable use of extra salt in the diet, higher prevalence of high waist circumference among females and also a high prevalence of hypertension.

The current study showed a high prevalence of smoking tobacco use in males (39.3% in both sexes with 73.4% in the male sex) and a strikingly high prevalence of smokeless tobacco use (60%) in females. Singh et al showed tobacco users were 12.54 percent.¹⁹ Joshi MD et al showed current smokers were 10%.²⁰ A study in Bihar, India showed a 22.75 percent prevalence of smoking in both sexes and all social classes.²¹ The

prevalence of smoking is much higher in the current study. Another study in North India showed a higher prevalence of tobacco use among slum dwellers (men 48.3%, women 11.9%) than non-slum dwellers (men 35.2%, women 3.5%).²² This study finding is compatible with the current study. Bangladesh urban health survey 2006 showed the prevalence of smoking in the slum male population was 60%, a little less than the current study.²³

The present study showed a high prevalence of low physical activity (36.2%). The prevalence of low physical activity was more in females than males (40% versus 33%). The urban slum study in Nairobi, Kenya showed a lesser prevalence of low physical activity 20%.²⁰

The overall prevalence of overweight and obesity was 15.6% in this study. Females showed a higher prevalence of overweight compared to males (18.2% versus 13.3%). Also, females had a much higher prevalence of central obesity (45.5%). Bangladesh urban health survey 2006 showed the prevalence of overweight and obesity was 17%, (respectively 15%

and 7% in women and men).²³ Misra et al²⁴ and Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) task force study²⁵ reported a prevalence of overweight of 25 percent and 20 percent respectively in Delhi slums. A study in Kenya showed that 58.3% of women were either obese or overweight and 41.5% of females had high waist circumference.²⁶ The current study also showed a similar result.

The current study has a few limitations that need to be acknowledged. First, this study was conducted among the adult slum populations of one selected slum area in Dhaka, Bangladesh, which may not be representative of all the slum populations across Bangladesh. Secondly, as we had financial and time limitations, we couldn't conduct the third step of the WHO STEPS survey. Diabetes was diagnosed only by previous records. So, it is most likely that the actual prevalence of diabetes would be more than we got in this study. Also, it is reasonable to think that the actual prevalence of drinking wine and women smoking would be more, as our cultural and social norms would prevent anyone to disclose this information.

Conclusion

This study showed a high prevalence of cardiovascular disease risk factors like smoking tobacco among male and female slum residents, low physical activity, very minimum fruit and vegetable intake with very high salt intake. We also noticed very high smokeless tobacco use and high waist circumference among females. Prevalence of hypertension was also found high. Reducing these risk factors will not only have a positive effect on cardiovascular diseases but will also have wide-reaching beneficial effects on other chronic non-communicable diseases. Preventive efforts in this population targeting behavioral lifestyle changes to curtail these risk factors are urgently required.

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Disclosure

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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